

Combining data and models for decisions in precision agriculture

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1. Introduction

In the face of a growing world population, declining land reserves and climate change, there is an urgent need to increase the efficiency of the production of food. Precision agriculture (PA) is one of the pathways in which the efficiency of agriculture can be increased. The profitability and sustainability of production of potatoes in The Netherlands can be increased by at least 20% by employing a range of PA technologies that are currently available to commercial growers^{1,2}. The systematic collection and processing of data is the cornerstone of precision agriculture. On the one hand, these data are used to derive models that describe the effect of weather, soil, and management on crop growth. On the other hand, data and models are used to support decision-making about when and where to apply inputs: fertilizers, crop protection agents, and irrigation water.

2. Approach

We work with two complementary modelling methods. In the first method mechanistic, process-based simulation models are used. This kind of model can in many practical cases explain and predict crop production, but must first be properly parameterized for a specific farm, field, or part of field. A major challenge is to find appropriate parameter values for the soil without resorting to extensive, costly and time-consuming soil sampling. We use data that are available on a large scale, such as satellite and drone imagery, soil scans, and existing soil maps, to parameterise the mechanistic models.

In the second approach machine learning (ML) methods are used. Here there are two major challenges. One challenge is related to the sheer infinite number of states that an agricultural system can assume, which makes it hard to train an ML model. A second, related challenge is to collect sufficient data for training the ML models. We investigate whether mechanistic models can be used to reduce the

dimensionality of the problem by computing features with which the training dataset can be enriched.

3. Results

For mechanistic models, initial results show that the proposed method of parameterisation works well. This is true even when the calibration data are lacking in precision and/or accuracy, as long as a sufficient number of fields and/or years is used in the calibration. Likewise, for machine learning models, features calculated using mechanistic models increase the prediction accuracy. However, it often proves difficult to understand why a particular feature does or does not increase prediction accuracy.

4. Discussion

An agricultural field with a crop growing on it is an exceedingly complex system. Thus, even the most detailed mechanistic model is still only a much simplified representation of reality and will fail to reproduce the original system's behaviour under certain conditions. An ML model does not even attempt to represent the structure of the modelled system, but aims only to reproduce the outputs. In both kinds of models there is a complex interplay between model structure and parameterisation, in that a particular change in model behaviour can often be achieved by changing the model structure, the model parameters, or both. This equifinality is a major concern when parameterising a mechanistic model or training an ML model.

References

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